

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins. Part XVI¹. Synthesis of 4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene Derivatives.

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7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin on bromination and hydrolysis gave 6-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (IIa) and its 2-carboxylic acid derivative. (IIa) and (IIc), on condensation with sodium and ethyl carbonate gave 4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene and its 5'-carboethoxy derivative respectively. 4-Hydroxy-3',4',8-trimethylpsoralene and its 5'-carboethoxy derivative were similarly prepared from 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin.

In continuation of our work on synthesis of furo coumarins, we report here the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene derivatives. Dholakia and Trivedi² reported the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene and 4-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo(2,3-h) benzopyran and u.v. spectrum of the former indicates that the compound is likely to possess photodynamic activity³. It was therefore, thought of interest to synthesise 4-hydroxycoumarins having furan ring fused to benzenoid part of the coumarin moiety having methyl group located at 4'-position and to record their u.v. spectra to study the relationship between structure and photodynamic activity of these compounds. *o*-Hydroxyacylbenzofuran derivatives are prepared by the alkaline hydrolysis of the corresponding 3-bromocoumarin derivatives and 4-hydroxy- α -pyrone ring is built upon them by the action of sodium and ethyl carbonate according to the method of Boyd and Robertson⁴.

7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin⁵ on bromination with bromine in acetic acid gave 3-bromo-7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin(Ia). This on hydrolysis with aqueous sodium carbonate underwent ring contraction to yield a mixture of 6-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (IIa) and the corresponding 2-carboxylic acid derivative, which on esterification with dimethyl sulphate in the presence of sodium bicarbonate gave the Me-6-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran-2-carboxylate (IIc). (IIa) on heating with pulverised sodium and ethyl carbonate according to the method of Boyd and Robertson⁴ gave 4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIa). Similarly (IIc) was converted to 5'-carbo-methoxy-4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIc). 7-Hydroxy-6-propionyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin⁶ on similar series of reactions afforded 4-hydroxy-3,4',8-trimethyl-psoralene (IIIb) and 5'-carbomethoxy-4-hydroxy-3,4',8-trimethylpsoralene which was acetylated to 5'-carbomethoxy-4-acetoxy-3,4',8-trimethylpsoralene (IIIg). The u.v. spectra of (IIIa), (IIIb), (IIIc) and (IIIg) are recorded and are also characterised by their acetoxy derivatives (IIId), (IIIe), (IIIf) and (IIIg) the structures of which are further confirmed, by I.R. Spectra.

- 3 -

I

II

III

IV

- a : R = H
b : R = CH₃

I

- a : R = R₁ = H
b : R = CH₃, R₁ = H
c : R = H; R₁ = COOCH₃
d : R = CH₃; R₁ = COOCH₃

II

- a : R = R₁ = R₂ = H
b : R = CH₃; R₁ = R₂ = H
c : R = R₂ = H; R₁ = COOCH₃
d : R = R₁ = H; R₂ = COCH₃
e : R = CH₃; R₁ = H; R₂ = COCH₃
f : R = H; R₁ = COOCH₃; R₂ = COCH₃
g : R = CH₃; R₁ = COOCH₃; R₂ = COCH₃

III

EXPERIMENTAL

I.R. Spectra were recorded with Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer in *nujol*.

The U.V. Spectra were recorded with Beckmann DU Spectrophotometer.

3-Bromo-7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (Ia): To a solution of 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (4.3 g.; 0.01 M) in hot glacial acetic acid (30 ml.), a solution of bromine in acetic acid (15 ml.; 20%; 0.01 M) was added in portions and was shaken for 15 mins. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 249°. Yield 3.0 g. (Found : Br, 25.80%. C₁₃H₁₁O₄Br requires Br, 25.72%).

6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (IIa) and Me-6-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran-2-carboxylate (IIc): 3-Bromo-7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (2 g.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate solution (50 ml.; 10%) for 3 hr. The separated product (IIa) on cooling, was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 100°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 70.57; H, 5.67. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.60; H, 5.88%). The filtrate on acidification gave a mixture of (IIa) and the corresponding 2-carboxylic acid derivative which was purified by treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution was esterified to (IIc) as follows: A mixture of 6-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (1 g.; 0.01 M), dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.; 0.01 M) and dry sodium bicarbonate (5 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml.) in a water bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and acetone was distilled off. The product obtained was further purified by passing over a short column of alumina in benzene. Evaporation of the solvent gave a solid which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 209°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 64.25; H, 5.13. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.12; H, 5.34%).

4-Hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIa): 6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (1 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of diethylcarbonate (15 ml.) by shaking. The solution was carefully added to pulverised sodium (2 g.) and the reaction mixture was heated in a water bath for 5 hr. After cooling, excess of sodium was decomposed by slow addition of alcohol (25 ml.). The contents were poured into ice water and ether extracted to remove unreacted compounds. The aqueous layer on acidification gave (IIIa) which was filtered. It was purified by treating it with sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitating it by hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 312°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.40; H, 4.08. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.81; H, 4.34%).

λ_{max} (ethanol) 236 nm (\log_{ϵ} 3.55); 297 (3.23). Acetoxy derivative (IIIId) prepared as usual, m.p. 211°. (Found: C, 65.94; H, 4.28. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.41%).

3,3'-Methylene bis(4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene (IV): 4-Hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene (0.1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (5 ml.). The solution was filtered, formalin (0.5 ml.; 40% solution) was added and was refluxed in a water bath for 30 mins. The separated product was filtered hot and dried, m.p. 326° (decomp.). Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 68.37; H, 4.10. $C_{27}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 68.64; H, 4.23%).

5'-Carbomethoxy-4-hydroxy-4',8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIc): Me-6-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran-2-carboxylate (IIc) (0.9 g.) dissolved in distilled diethylcarbonate (15 ml.) was slowly added to pulverised sodium (1 g.) and the reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 6 hr. The mixture was worked up as before. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 359°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 62.44; H, 4.58. $C_{15}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 62.63; H, 4.13%).

λ_{max} (ethanol) 254 nm (\log_{ϵ} 4.25); 282 (4.1), 322 (4.08). Acetoxy derivative prepared as usual (IIIe), m.p. 281°. (Found: C, 61.79; H, 4.21. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 61.81; H, 4.24%).

3-Bromo-7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (Ib): To a solution of 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (5 g.) in hot acetic acid, a solution of bromine in acetic acid (18 ml.; 20%; 0.01 M) was added in portions with shaking. The separated product

was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 223°. Yield 3 g. (Found : Br, 24.81; $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Br$ requires Br, 24.61%).

6-Hydroxy-5-propionyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (IIb) and Me-6-hydroxy-5-propionyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran-2-carboxylate (IIId) : 3-Bromo-7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (3 g.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate solution (25 ml.; 10%) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate was allowed to cool. The product (IIb) was worked out as before. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 120°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 71.22; H, 6.37. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.55; H, 6.42%). The filtrate on acidification gave a mixture of (IIb) and the corresponding 2-carboxylic acid derivative which was purified by treating it with sodium bicarbonate solution as before and methylated with dimethyl sulphate and sodium bicarbonate as before to (IIId). It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 172°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 64.88; H, 5.49. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.21; H, 5.79%).

4-Hydroxy-3,4',8-trimethylpsoralene (IIIb) : 6-Hydroxy-5-propionyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (1 g.) was dissolved in diethylcarbonate (10 ml.) and the solution was carefully poured into pulverised sodium (2 g.). The reaction mixture was heated in a water bath for 6 hr. and was worked up as before. The product (IIIb) crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 302°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 68.82; H, 4.71. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.91%).

λ_{max} (ethanol) 235 nm (\log_e 3.47); 304 (3.18); 315 (3.16).

Acetoxy derivative prepared as usual (IIIIf) m.p. 204°. (Found : C, 66.85; H, 4.79. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 67.13; H, 4.89%).

I.R. Spectrum showed two strong bands in the carbonyl region viz. 1770 cm^{-1} (acetoxy group at position 4); 1715 cm^{-1} (lactone $> C = O$ group).

5'-Carbomethoxy-4-acetoxy-3,4',8-trimethylpsoralene (IIIg) : Me-6-hydroxy-5-propionyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran-2-carboxylate (0.8 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethyl carbonate (7 ml.). The solution was added to pulverised sodium (2 g.) and the reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 6 hr. On working out the reaction as described earlier gave 5'-carbomethoxy-4-hydroxy-3,4',8-trimethylpsoralene which was soluble in sodium bicarbonate, m.p. $> 300^\circ$. It did not crystallise from any common solvents, hence directly acetylated as follows : 5'-carbomethoxy-5-hydroxy-3,4',8-trimethylpsoralene (0.5 g.), acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were mixed and refluxed on a sand bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and allowed to stand. The solid which separated was filtered, washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution followed by water. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 340° (decomp.). Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 62.34; H, 4.22. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79; H, 4.65%).

I.R. Spectrum showed three bands in the carbonyl region viz., 1765 cm^{-1} (acetoxy group at position 4), 1735 cm^{-1} (lactone $> C = O$ gr.) and 1680 cm^{-1} (carboethoxy gr. at position 5').

λ_{max} (ethanol) 260 nm (\log_e 3.55); 309 (3.15); 335 (3.05).

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R E F E R E N C E S

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